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 VIRTUAL

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Diverse Responses of USRN Members to COVID-19: Diversity and Trends beyond the Academia

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Abstract

The University Social Responsibility Network (USRN) promotes civic engagement in higher education through a broad understanding of the concept of University Social Responsibility (USR). In 2019, the USRN launched a joint initiative to raise awareness about the importance and diversity of good practices among universities in their engagements with society. The project resulted in a Massive Open Online Course, titled *Introduction to University Social Responsibility*, that introduces general theory and practices. The Coronavirus disease 2019 pandemic slowed down the course implementation but also created a new opportunity for universities to demonstrate their commitment to addressing pressing social issues in all corners of the world. A *Special Session on Universities' Response* was added to the original course, portraying several of the strategies that universities took to address the challenges brought by the pandemic. A total of 13 USRN members shared their academic and non-academic projects. These initiatives demonstrate very diverse forms of engagement as research, education, advisory role, outreach, information management, provision of support, institutional reforms and extended services. By reflecting on these experiences, this study classifies the kinds of engagements that can in turn facilitate the decision making of universities' leaders for their own USR strategies.

Keywords: University Social Responsibility, COVID-19, response, higher education, non-academic, civic engagement

1. Introduction

During its 4th Executive Committee Meeting in 2018 in Haifa, Israel, the members of the University Social Responsibility Network (USRN) agreed to collaborate on producing a joint Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) to raise awareness on the concept of University Social Responsibility (USR) while promoting the visibility of good practices carried out by universities in the network. Kyoto University and The Hong Kong Polytechnic University led the production of the MOOC, titled *Introduction to University Social Responsibility* (hereafter stated as the MOOC), organized in four modules¹ that cover general theory and practices of social engagement by institutions in the higher education sector. The syllabus and information shared for the Special Session are available in the MOOC's website in edX².

The production of the MOOC was underway when Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) hit and started to spread in early 2020. Many universities around the world stepped up their civic engagements to face the emerging challenges as the pandemic unfolded, and in July of 2020, the USRN decided to add a new module to the MOOC to present the responses of universities to COVID-19.

¹ MOOC's syllabus <https://www.edx.org/course/introduction-to-university-social-responsibility>

² MOOC <https://www.edx.org/course/introduction-to-university-social-responsibility>

The new module followed the structure set by a project initiated by the USRN Secretariat as a mini website³ that showcased members responses. This module was added to the MOOC as a stand-alone unit called *Special Session on University Response to COVID-19* (hereafter stated as Special Session). As a result, the MOOC is currently structured as follows:

Graph 1: Structure of the MOOC on USR

The Special Session was the source of inspiration and data for this study, and encompasses the narratives describing initiatives shared by the following universities: Al-Farabi Kazakh National University (AFKNU) in Kazakhstan; Beijing Normal University (BNU), The Hong Kong Polytechnic University (HKPU), and Sichuan University (SU) in China; University of Haifa (UoH) in Israel; Kyoto University (KU) in Japan; The University of Manchester (UoM) in the United Kingdom; University of São Paulo (USP) in Brazil; University of Pretoria (UoP) in South Africa; Tufts University (TU) and Washington University in St. Louis (WUSL) in the United States; University of New South Wales (UNSW) in Australia; and Simon Fraser University (SFU) in Canada (Palacio & Sadehvandi, 2022).

Based on the notion that USR can be defined as the shared responsibility of universities to address challenges and to advance societies, and that USR permeates all aspects in the life of universities (Shek & Hollister, 2017), the following pages identify areas and dimensions of how universities in the USRN faced the pandemic. The different kinds of USR initiatives that can be replicated in other universities beyond the USRN are identified, thereby offering an analytical framework to facilitate policy design at the higher education sector when approaching risk and disaster management with a comprehensive and proactive mindset.

2. Literature Review

COVID-19 reaffirmed the notion that universities have a key role in the society; the calamities brought about by the pandemic increased their academic contributions and research in related areas has grown since 2020 (Cai et al., 2021). Universities, however, have also served other key functions such as identifying and synergizing resources while having to ensure safety and continuity in their own services (Cutter et al., 2021). As social distance protocols were set in place, universities produced various reactions, such as through pedagogical innovation and curricular development to face lockdowns, especially through the implementation of online education (Hale et al., 2020; Yang & Huang, 2021).

For universities, the pandemic represented major challenges but also opportunities for new research, innovative education, and renewed approaches to management and engagement (Beech & Anseel, 2020). COVID-19 also helped expand and deepen the existing knowledge and to rethink the role of universities in disaster situations (Marinoni et al., 2020).

³ USRN' COVID-19 Response minisite <https://covid19.usrnetwork.org>

As socially sensitive institutions, universities face and address emerging social and environmental challenges by reinventing themselves through reform. These reforms tend to bring a sense of social responsibility not only into their academic work but also into other functions that connect them with real problems (Larrán & Andrades Peña, 2017). Universities act responsibly in how they behave and govern themselves, by offering quality services, applying ethical rules, or by engaging in philanthropic projects (Tetřevová & Sabolova, 2010).

Universities may also be reacting to introducing more USR-oriented policies due to the growing relevance as an indicator in university rankings (Shek & Hollister, 2017). In this sense, the pandemic represented a new opportunity for universities to promote their social engagement. Examples of this are the universities' interest to deepen exchanges with society, reinforced creativity, or new training spaces for students (Rababah et al., 2021).

Literature on universities' responses to COVID-19 suggests that USR is multi-layered and includes a wide range of engagements beyond the academia (Ifijeh & Yusuf, 2020). For example, universities addressed human rights that denounce the stigmatization of people infected, whose personal information was disclosed by governments and the media (Yoshioka & Maeda, 2020).

USR programmes are often closely tied to the values, priorities, and specific circumstances of each institution. This recognition emphasizes the need for USR to be tailored to any university's capacities, willingness to adopt management principles, teaching, research practices, and engagement efforts that address real-world challenges (Sánchez et al., 2013). The approaches and programmes related to USR highlights that its interpretation varies significantly across universities. This diversity underscores the notion that each university has its own unique context and vision, influencing how they understand and implement their USR strategies (Palacio & Choy, 2019).

Given its context, this study follows the same line of thought of the USRN members, who agree in understanding USR as a wide-ranging and evolving concept that describes the shared responsibility of universities to contribute to social betterment by integrating social responsibility policies into their institutional management, teaching, research, services and public activities (Shek & Hollister, 2017).

3. Method

The data for this article consists of the initiatives of USRN members in response to the pandemic. Data collection occurs in two steps. First, the USRN Secretariat gathered information from the members to share their responses and good practices, and showcased them in a mini-site at the USRN portal⁴. The second step relates to the decision to add the Special Session on Universities' Responses to COVID-19 to the MOOC when the production team invited USRN members to provide further information. Universities were free to choose and submit the data they deem relevant in any format.

The data consists of materials such as videos, websites and texts describing universities' efforts to address the pandemic and were organised by resource persons in each university. The information shared by each institution represents a stand-alone unit in the Special Session, but when integrated and analysed transversally, can offer an overview of trends regarding universities' responses, motivations and priorities.

The starting point of the study are the narratives shared by the universities in the Special Session, that are first divided into blocks of text (describing areas of engagement) and then into items (individual actions) that help to quantify and identify priorities through a trend analysis.

⁴ USRN mini site on Universities Response to COVID-19 <https://covid19.usrnetwork.org/>

Texts with related information are grouped into the following areas of engagement: Research, Education, Advisory Role, Civic Engagement, Information Management, Provision of Support, Structural Reforms and Extended Services. Subsequently, several areas are divided into dimensions and sub-dimensions to offer depth in their details. The quantification of data occurred as follows:

Graph 2: Quantification of data from narratives to block, items, and areas

4. Observations: Diverse USR approaches

Based on the projects enacted to address the COVID-19 pandemic by 13 universities in the USRN that are located in five different continents and engage with different contexts, this study accomplished global representation. The study systematises areas of engagement with dimensions and subdimensions, identifies individual actions that can be quantified and shows trends regarding the priorities of the selected universities.

The universities reacted to the pandemic in different yet related ways, depending on what each institution values the most in terms of their meaning of *being socially responsible* means, thus corroborating the notion that USR is relative to each university’s vision, priorities, and context. At the same time, based on the diverse nature of the initiatives shared in the MOOC, a clear line can be drawn differentiating *traditional academic contributions*—research and education—from *non-academic forms of engagement*, which in turn demonstrate these universities’ drive to go the extra mile (Palacio & Sadehvandi, 2022).

Despite limitations in terms of its potential for generalization (given that the data comprise a list of curated responses) rather than an exhaustive compilation of policies and initiatives, this study presents a significant contribution through its innovative method to reduce and analyse qualitative data into quantitative and measurable actions. Beyond treating the responses as mere narratives, the study quantified the information by breaking down their texts into measurable elements that can reflect trends about the universities’ options to design and implement USR policy and activities.

4.1 Diverse Forms and Depths of Engagement

The first empirical observation from the data in the MOOC was the diverse mindset and strategies of universities to address different aspects of the pandemic and the needs of the communities they serve. For easy comprehension, the different approaches were categorised according to their shared features. Once identified, these areas of engagement were then divided into dimensions based on different aspects.

Graph 3: Areas and Dimensions of Engagement

Graph 3 integrates all the identified areas and highlights the role of universities as a source of social responsibility, where their policies result from the rational decision of their managers and staff, and where the areas of engagement are connected to each other. The areas were organised as follows:

1. Research: a) Health impact, and b) Socio-economic-environmental impact
2. Education: a) Class format; b) New contents; c) Training; and d) Technical aspects
3. Advisory role: a) Risk management in universities, b) Partnerships, and c) Inclusion
4. Outreach: a) Institutional engagement, and b) Alternative resources
5. Information management: a) Internal sharing, and b) Communication outside campus
6. Support: a) For students, b) For staff, and c) For external communities
7. Reforms: a) New bodies, b) Risk management, c) “Channel” support, and d) administration
8. Extended services: a) Library, b) Museums, c) Research centers, and d) Other facilities

The graph shows that civic engagements greatly exceed academic contributions and take several forms as non-academic contributions. Data in the study revealed that from the areas of engagement, only two—education and research—are academic in nature, and the combined items identified for these areas accounted for 31% of the total. The other six areas portrayed non-academic initiatives and made up the remaining 69% of all items.

4.2 Trends in USR Engagements as Response to the COVID-19 pandemic

The blocks of text from the narratives used above to identify the areas and dimensions were then divided into smaller segments (items) depending on the nature of their information. Thus, 751 individual items were identified and then distributed back into the areas and dimensions to which they belonged.

Based on this quantification of narratives, the analysis of trends highlighted the relative priorities of universities and revealed the relative significance of each kind of engagement in the responses. Table 1 shows the distribution of items per area of engagement, their dimensions and their relative participation to the entire set of contributions.

Table 1 provides evidence about the areas of engagement these universities prioritised and how they distributed their resources and efforts. Although outside the goals of this study, by applying this process to the data provided by each individual university, the priorities and areas of interest of each institution can also be identified and analysed individually and in the context of the USRN.

When comparing the absolute number of items identified (751) to those that were allocated to each area of engagement, the largest contributions fell under Research with 182 entries and Outreach with 138 entries. The rest follows in order: Support with 104, Advisory role with 91, Information management with 81, Structural reforms with 69, Education with 52, and finally Extended services with 34.

Areas of engagement Items / Percentage to the total	Dimensions of engagement	Items per dimension	Trends
Research 182 / 24.2%	1.1 Health impact	86	11.5%
	1.2 Socio-economic-environmental impact	96	12.8%
Education 52 / 6.9%	2.1 Online class formats (safety and access)	7	0.9%
	2.2 New, and in-focus contents	26	3.5%
	2.3 Training for teachers	10	1.3%
	2.4 Technical aspects of moving online	9	1.2%
Advisory role 91 / 12.2%	3.1 Risk management internally in the universities	26	3.5%
	3.2 Partnerships with other organizations	48	6.4%
	3.3 Inclusion of minorities and communities at risk	17	2.3%
Outreach 138 / 18.4%	4.1 Institutional engagement and partnerships	82	10.9%
	4.2 Alternative resources: volunteers and fundraising	56	7.5%
Information management 81 / 10.8%	5.1 Internal mechanisms for information sharing	34	4.5%
	5.2 Communication with partners outside university	47	6.3%
Support 104 / 13.8%	6.1 Alternative relief for students	25	3.3%
	6.2 Alternative relief for staff	21	2.8%
	6.3 Support for external communities	58	7.7%
Structural reforms 69 / 9.2%	7.1 New bodies and mechanisms	28	3.7%
	7.2 Risk prevention and crisis management	17	2.3%
	7.3 Channeling support	9	1.2%
	7.4 Administrative bodies to channel external support	15	2.0%
Extended services 34 / 4.5%	8.1 Library and academic resources	7	0.9%
	8.2 Museums and cultural facilities	4	0.5%
	8.3 Research centers and related facilities	8	1.1%
	8.4 Other facilities	15	2.0%
Total		751	100%

Table 1. Estimation of trends by areas and dimensions of engagement

Graph 4 visually shows the distribution of the items per area, which is indicative of the relative priority each area of engagement received from the universities in terms of items (as individual actions or efforts) and percentage to the total items identified based on the information shared in the Special Session of the MOOC by the USRN members. Academic contributions (research and education) have been marked in dark colour for emphasis.

Research 182 / 24.2%	Information management 81 / 10.8%	Structural reforms 69 / 9.2%	Outreach 138 / 18.4%	Support 104 / 13.8%
	Education 52 / 6.9%	Extended services 34 / 4.5.%		Advisory role 91 / 12.2%

Graph 4: Priority areas engagement in the responses to COVID-19

Observable trends that can be depicted from the graph refer to the relative smaller number of academic contributions as compared with non-academic ones. As shown by the darker colour in the graph, academic contributions (research and education) combined account for approximately 31% of the initiatives reported while non-academic contributions represented approximately 69% of the remaining initiatives presented in the Special Session.

From such information, universities cannot be inferred to give less priority to their academic work and the value of their contributions; however, these figures (31% versus 69%) are very telling in terms of the efforts the universities decided to share as their most representative forms of response to the pandemic in the Special Session of the MOOC.

When looking in detail into the specific information in each area of engagement, the data show that Research, as an area of engagement, achieved almost a quarter (24.2%) of all items identified. This result is related to the fact that these universities are research-intensive institutions, and thus they gave priority to their research work as a form of response to the pandemic.

Research obtained the largest number of dimensions and sub-dimensions, which is indicative of its complexity as a form of response. The dimensions identified referred to Research on: (1) Health impact, which included the sub-dimensions of a) development of new products, b) Mathematical modelling, c) New technologies, and d) Mental health; and (2) Socio-economic-environmental impact, which included the sub-dimensions of a) Contention of spread of virus and b) Economic, social and environmental impacts and recovery.

The next observable trend is that Outreach, as a form of engagement referring to the interactions of universities with society outside the campus, came up second in the list with almost 18.4% of initiatives as response. This result is indicative that these institutions gave priority to collaborations and partnerships to respond to the pandemic by engaging with local, regional, national and international communities and stakeholders, particularly with partners outside of academia.

Similar to Research, Outreach also had a large number of dimensions that suggest complex forms of interactions. The dimensions identified for this area refer to: (1) Institutional engagement and partnerships, which included the sub-dimensions of a) Production and distribution of medical goods, b) Strategic networking, and c) Dispatching health and other professionals; and (2) Tapping on alternative resources, which included the sub-dimensions of a) Promotion and organization of volunteer activities and b) Fundraising efforts.

Support came up third in the list of areas of engagement, with 13.8% of items describing initiatives that the universities mainly implemented through administrative procedures. Based on the beneficiaries, the following dimensions were identified as Support for: a) Students; b) Staff; and c) External communities.

Advisory role, as an area of engagement, accounted for 12.2% of the items identified. This area portrays initiatives in which universities fostered relations with society by offering technical advice and research output to their own communities and policy makers, such as governments, inter-governmental agencies and organizations or the public. Advisory role include three dimensions: a) Risk management in universities, b) Partnerships and c) Inclusion.

Information management received 10.8% of the items identified, and reflected the initiatives of universities to boost the production, gathering and dissemination of critical information related to the pandemic. This area is divided into two dimensions, namely, a) Internal information share and b) Communication outside campus.

Structural reforms accounted for 9.2% of the items identified and referred to how the universities adapted and updated their institutional organizations, internal governance methods and management styles to respond to the pandemic by promoting more efficient information share, decision making and implementation. As an area of engagement, Structural reforms was divided into four dimensions, including a) New bodies, b) Risk management, c) Support of other organizations as a channel, and d) Effective administration.

Education obtained only 6.9% of the items identified from the narratives describing the universities' responses to the pandemic in the Special Session. This result does not necessarily imply that universities did not make major contributions in this area; rather, efforts focused on ensuring continuity and quality in the delivery of education mainly through online learning, triggering a whole new area of support and innovation.

Education, being a core mission of every university, stands out as a clear domain to produce social impacts. The pandemic presented a major challenge to all educational institutions, yet universities were resilient and found new ways to grow, revise and to re-envision themselves. Education was divided in four dimensions that reflect the diversity of actions taken and described: a) Class formats, b) New contents, c) Training and skill development, and d) Technical aspects.

Lastly, Extended services obtained 4.5% of the items identified, and going beyond the more typical forms of engagement, these universities mentioned unusual yet very relevant, efforts to serve their communities and society through their services. Initiatives in this area were perhaps less visible, but very valuable. The dimensions included a) Library and other resources, b) Museums and cultural facilities, c) Research centres and related facilities, and d) Other facilities.

Overall, the narratives describing the responses to the pandemic by these universities represent a wide range of innovative solutions and approaches to the different problems and challenges these universities faced because of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Notably, at this point, the information shared in the Special Session of the MOOC on USR only represents examples of proactive policies and good practices to promote the positive impacts of universities on society at large. By no means must the data in this study be considered as a comprehensive or exhaustive inventory or measures implemented by the universities examined in this study; instead, the experiences described in the MOOC can serve as a source of inspiration for all universities seeking to boost their own social roles and impacts.

5. Conclusion

Experiences shared by the universities in the USRN through the MOOC, and particularly in the Special Session on Responses to the COVID-19 pandemic, offer ample space for reflection and learning, not only for the meaning of the USR concept but also in terms of its diverse understanding, depth of its implication and the need to further include the factors and elements beyond the academic contributions of universities in the analysis of USR policies.

General observations resulting from this study relate to the fact that USR permeates all aspects in the life of universities, and crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic serve as clear evidence that socially engaged universities can make valuable social impacts on policies and projects aimed to reduce risk and manage crises. Universities can also be major drivers of change as they offer safe environments to their own communities, representing not only secure spaces in themselves but also promoting good practices that are replicable in settings beyond their campus.

Despite the severity of the calamities brought by the COVID-19 crisis, universities not only showed resilience in their drive to continue their work, but also became proactive parts of the solution to problems in a very wide range of ways. The responses of these universities to the pandemic demonstrate a shared sense of responsibility among members of the USRN, and corroborate that the USR concept and its implications are intimately related to each institution's mission and context.

Key findings from this study relate to the need to reconsider USR as a wider concept, a notion that is more open, inclusive and encompassing to the real diversity of options in terms of policy and measures that universities have at hand to serve their communities. This study reveals that in times of crisis such as the COVID-19 pandemic, universities can diversify their own pool of engagements in at least eight academic and non-academic areas of engagement with dimensions that produce deep and wide social impacts.

Another key contribution of this study is the creation of a new framework of analysis that not only allows to identify areas of responses where universities engage in, but more importantly a means to help universities spot and determine USR priorities based on how they allocate their efforts and initiatives.

The study provides evidence of the influence and connection between academic and non-academic engagements in relation to applying USR to all aspects of the life of universities. While conventional perspectives primarily associate USR with education and research, this study—despite limitations—reveals that non-academic contributions significantly outweigh the academic ones. The combined percentage of Education- and Research-related initiatives accounted for only 31.1% of all the items identified, indicating that the majority of responses to the pandemic are non-academic projects or initiatives.

By examining the responses of universities to the pandemic and quantifying their institutional efforts, this study provides new insights into their decision making and the underlying priorities that shape their endeavours. While the application of these findings universally to the entire higher education sector may be challenging, this study presents a starting point to better comprehend the real impact of the USRN members on the disruptive event of the pandemic.

6. Future Research

This study may motivate and prompt new research in related areas that include but are not limited to the development of new frameworks that can help assess the measures implemented by universities to address the COVID-19 pandemic or other disruptions and disasters. Further research must be encouraged regarding innovative approaches that challenge traditional and limited understandings of USR and its implications, or in policy design and decision making on how USR can be incorporated in other areas of the life of universities.

7. Acknowledgments

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